

**Book review of “Acceptance, Participation, Solidarity. The Importance of the Interdisciplinary Approach”
by Ewa Dąbrowa, Warsaw 2024, 200 pp.**

Maria Czubak¹

Abstract

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¹ The Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland ORCID: 0009-0007-5780-9475,
E-mail: mc67500@aps.edu.pl

Acceptance, participation, and solidarity are three issues guiding the work of those working for inclusiveness. Each of them plays a relevant role in the process of creating an inclusive society in which each person's voice is heard and considered equally. These concepts are inseparable from the issue of social exclusion. Social exclusion is a complex problem that requires an interdisciplinary approach to find solutions. Such an approach makes it possible to take a broader view and better understand the needs of disadvantaged groups. This perspective is also promoted by the book *Acceptance, Participation, Solidarity. The Importance of an Interdisciplinary Approach*.

Published in 2024 the book frequently references the current political situation and contemporary social issues. The authors of the various chapters from different countries offer a multidimensional view of the situation of socially excluded people. At the same time, it highlights the universal nature of inclusiveness while highlighting locally relevant issues.

The book consists of two parts. They are preceded by the book's opening chapter written by Anna Odrowąż-Coates. This chapter introduces a multidimensional reflection on the possibility of promoting social inclusion and presents the issue from economic and social policy perspectives. The author also points out existing tools that should be used to promote social inclusion.

The first part of the book, *Inclusiveness as a "Hidden Treasure" of Disability Studies*, presents the situation of people with disabilities concerning various dimensions of social life. The topics such as art therapy, vocational and social rehabilitation, and preparation for independent living, are described. Research on the leisure activities of adults with mental disabilities is also presented with conclusions encouraging the promotion of active creativity over passive consumption of content. The issue of multiple discrimination, to which people with disabilities are particularly vulnerable, is also addressed, along with the description of legislation regarding the possibility of marriage for people with intellectual disabilities. Some of these topics do not immediately come to mind when thinking about people with disabilities. This shows the scale of the changes that need to be made. People with disabilities should be seen by society as individuals like non-disabled, rather than being seen as their disabilities.

The second part of the book, *From Solidarity to Integration: Challenges in Interdisciplinary Studies*, focuses on social exclusion for reasons other than disability. Two chapters depicting the performance of universities were an important part. One examines the inclusion efforts of Ukrainian universities as perceived by students with war trauma, while the other presents ways in which universities in Ukraine and other European countries include students with disabilities in the educational process and social life. Other chapters explore topics such as application of capability theory in addressing the problems of excluded groups or ways to support prisoners during and after serving their sentences, the treat oof suicide affecting people from disadvantaged groups and the role of prevention among such individuals.

Although all chapters deal with social inclusion, the thematic scope is much broader. Some measures are deemed to enable and accelerate the building of an inclusive society. People from excluded groups are portrayed as potential capable creators in charge of their own

lives, rather than passive receivers of the actions of others. At the same time, the authors do not shy away from sad realities. The chapters point out that the chance of quickly moving away from the reproduction of exclusionary stereotypes is minor. They also emphasize the need for ongoing improvement of actions that have been already considered effective.

The book promotes the use of an interdisciplinary perspective in addressing on social exclusion and fostering an inclusive society. The authors explore several thematic areas, highlighting in the multifaceted nature of the phenomenon and the necessity of taking comprehensive measures in favour of disadvantaged groups. As a result, the book becomes a call to action, advocating for various ways to strive for a more just world. At the same time, it reveals wide research perspectives within the intersectional paradigm of important and extremely complex social issues. Intersectionality, which emerged from the critical approach, allows for the identification of the invisible phenomena and uncovering of the multifactorial determinants of social inequality and exclusion. This should be considered the basis for social change in regards of acceptance, participation and solidarity.